

Rosmarinic acid attenuates obesity and obesity-related inflammation in human adipocytes

Lily V. Vasileva^a, Martina S. Savova^{a,b}, Daniel Tews^c, Martin Wabitsch^c, Milen I. Georgiev^{a,b,*}

^a Department of Plant Cell Biotechnology, Center of Plant Systems Biology and Biotechnology, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

^b Laboratory of Metabolomics, The Stephan Angeloff Institute of Microbiology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

^c Division of Pediatric Endocrinology and Diabetes, Department of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine, Ulm University Medical Center, Ulm, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Handling editor: Dr. Jose Luis Domingo

Keywords:

Rosmarinic acid
Adipocytes
Obesity
Inflammation
Anti-Adipogenic action

Chemical compounds used in this study:

Rosmarinic acid (PubChem CID: 5281792)
Orlistat (PubChem CID: 3034010)

ABSTRACT

Chronic low-grade inflammation is a hallmark of obesity and its related metabolic disorders. At the same time signaling from pro-inflammatory factors such as transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β) or interleukin 17A (IL-17A) are proposed as crucial for the commitment of fibroblast progenitor cells towards adipogenic differentiation. Modulation of inflammation during adipogenic differentiation is incompletely explored as a potential approach to prevent metabolic disorders. Rosmarinic acid (RA) is a caffeic acid derivative known for its anti-inflammatory effects. Experimental studies of its activity on adipogenic factors or *in vivo* obesity models are, however, controversial and hence insufficient. Here, we investigated the anti-adipogenic action of RA in human Simpson-Golabi-Behmel syndrome (SGBS) adipocytes. Gene expression levels of key players in adipogenesis and lipid metabolism were assessed. Furthermore, a molecular mechanism of action was proposed. The most prominent effect was found on the translation of C/EBP α , PPAR γ and adiponectin, as well as on the modulation of *TGF1B* and *IL17A*. Interestingly, involvement of NRF2 signaling was identified upon RA treatment. In summary, our findings indicate that RA prevents inflammation and excessive lipid accumulation in human adipocytes. Data from the molecular analysis demonstrate that RA has potential for treatment of obesity and obesity-related inflammation.

1. Introduction

Obesity is among the most persistent health problems of the world population in the last decades. The prognosis is poor concerning the management of weight control for the next 50 years, due to the high rates of maternal and childhood obesity (Blucher, 2019). Moreover, the progress established within clarification of obesity pathogenesis did not result in significant improvements in the pharmacotherapy options (Vasileva et al., 2018). Overweight and obesity refer to excessive and/or ectopic fat accumulation in the human body, which is associated with a large number of chronic diseases such as type 2 diabetes, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, elevated blood glucose, insulin resistance, cardiovascular diseases, dyslipidemia, hypertension, polycystic ovary syndrome, higher risk of carcinogenesis as well as accompanying low-grade chronic inflammation (Blucher, 2019; Boutens et al., 2018; Vasileva et al., 2018, 2020).

Adipose tissue is long recognized for its endocrine function along

with its energy maintenance and storage capacity (Lin et al., 2020; Vasileva et al., 2018). In response to pro-adipogenic stimulation adipocytes react by increasing cell number (hyperplasia) and size (hypertrophy). The physiological recruitment of preadipocytes for adipogenic differentiation is critical for maintenance of healthy functioning fat tissue (Senol-Cosar et al., 2016; Shao et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020). Further, two opposing processes keep the balance of fat content in the adipose tissue: adipogenesis and lipolysis. Lipid turnover changes with age in favor of decreased lipolysis even with stable adipogenesis rates, suggesting that novel obesity management compounds should rather target inhibition of adipogenesis than acceleration of lipolysis (Arner et al., 2019). *De novo* adipogenesis of progenitor cells could be initiated upon external signaling from factors such as insulin, bone morphogenetic proteins, transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β), IL-17A, insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF1) and fibroblast growth factor 1 (Lin et al., 2020; Petrus et al., 2018; Shin et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2020). The orchestration of the adipogenic program is conducted by the key transcription factors CAAT/enhancer-binding protein alpha (C/EBP α),

* Corresponding author. Laboratory of Metabolomics, The Stephan Angeloff Institute of Microbiology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 139 Ruski Blvd., 4000, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

E-mail address: milengeorgiev@bgg.bg (M.I. Georgiev).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2021.112002>

Received 2 July 2020; Received in revised form 23 November 2020; Accepted 14 January 2021

Available online 19 January 2021

0278-6915/© 2021 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Abbreviations		ORO	Oil red O
ACC	acetyl-CoA carboxylase	ORST	orlistat
ADIPOQ	adiponectin	PGC1A	peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma co-activator 1 alpha
AMPK	adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase	PPAR	peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors
C/EBP	CAAT/enhancer-binding proteins	PS	penicillin/streptomycin
DMEM/F12	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium/Nutrient F-12 Ham	PVDF	polyvinylidene fluoride
FABP4	fatty acid binding protein 4	RA	rosmarinic acid
FASN	fatty acid synthase	RPL13A	ribosomal protein L13A
FBS	fetal bovine serum	RT	room temperature
HO-1	heme oxygenase 1	SGBS	Simpson-Golabi-Behmel syndrome
IBMX	3-isobutyl-1-methylxantine	SMAD	mothers against decapentaplegic homolog
IGF1	insulin growth factor	SREBP	sterol regulatory element-binding protein
IL	interleukin	TGF- β	transforming growth factor beta
NFE2L2	nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 gene	TNF- α	tumor necrosis factor alpha
NF κ B	nuclear factor kappa B	TUBB	tubulin
NRF2	nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2	UCP1	uncoupling protein 1

peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR γ), and the lipogenic factor sterol regulatory element-binding protein-1 (SREBP1), as central players. Further, the adipogenic transformation is characterized with increased expression in key adipogenic markers as adiponectin and the fatty acid binding protein 4 (FABP4). Additionally, the SREBP1 activity results in upregulation of genes involved in the lipid metabolic pathway such as acetyl-CoA carboxylase (ACC), fatty acid synthase (FASN) (Kroon et al., 2020; Vasileva et al., 2018; Okuno et al., 2018).

Strong evidence suggest that obesity-induced inflammation provokes a spectrum of metabolic dysregulations in the adipose tissue such as insulin resistance, lipotoxicity and increased oxidative burden (Kroon et al., 2020; Okuno et al., 2018; Petrus et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020;

Wueest et al., 2018). Overfed adipocytes in the context of obesity shift their adipokines profile towards inflammation, by increasing the secretion of interleukin (IL) -1 β , IL-6, IL-8, IL-29, tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), leptin, and resistin, thus provoking immune activation of the resident macrophages and subsequent formation of the vicious cycle of obesity-related inflammation (Boutens et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2020; Shin et al., 2009; Wueest et al., 2018). Regulation of the inflammatory response is governed mainly by the transcription factor nuclear factor kappa B (NF κ B, encoded by the *NFKB1* gene) which determines its implication in the development of obesity-induced complications (Lin et al., 2020; Wueest et al., 2018). Further, the transcription factor nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (NRF2, encoded by the *NFE2L2*

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of rosmarinic acid and schematic representation of the experimental design. Chemical name: (2R)-3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-[(E)-3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)prop-2-enyl]oxypropanoic acid; Mw 360.31 g/mol (a). Timeline of the study design in days (b).

gene), which serves as a master regulator of the cellular defense against oxidative damage, has been proposed to play a role in adipocytes metabolism (Barroso et al., 2015; Li et al., 2020; Vasileva et al., 2020). Recently, attention was drawn to the possibility of targeting obesity, and more specifically adipose tissue function, with anti-inflammatory compounds that also target adipogenic factors (Kim et al., 2020; Kroon et al., 2020; Petrus et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020).

Rosmarinic acid (RA) is an ester of caffeic acid and 3,4-dihydroxyphenyllactic acid (Fig. 1a), naturally synthesized through shikimate/phenylpropanoid pathway in plants. Caffeic acid ester derivatives are known with low lipophilicity and predictably hampered intracellular entry. Among this class of compounds, RA is considered as structurally interesting with regards to its high ability to interact with the cell membranes compared to other phenolic acids (Filipe et al., 2018). RA has been reported to possess diverse effects such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antifibrotic, anti-proliferative, hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, besides abundant neuro- and nephro-protective properties (Gerogianni et al., 2018; Rong et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018). The following signaling pathways emerged as the main targets of RA, i.e. the TNF- α -induced activation of NF κ B (Chen et al., 2018; Joardar et al., 2019; Seow and Lau, 2017), the adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK)/mothers against decapentaplegic homolog (SMAD3, Yang et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2018), and the NRF2/heme oxygenase 1 (HO-1) responses (Gerogianni et al., 2018; Rong et al., 2018). Counteraction of redox overload by decrease in superoxide dismutase and catalase in cardiac tissue was reported for RA treatment in obesity and type 2 diabetes models, along with a decrease in serum total cholesterol and glucose level (Zych et al., 2019). Hepatoprotective activity confirmed *in vivo* is supported with data for the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics parameters of RA in rats, both wild-type and with liver injury, which further indicates that RA has the relevant bioavailability profile for an oral application (Min et al., 2018). However, data on the metabolic effects of RA from human studies are yet to be assessed. Moreover, experimental studies evaluating the potential activity of RA on adipocytes function are insufficient and the available data appear inconclusive.

All above-summarized provoked our interest to study RA anti-adipogenic potential in human adipocytes. Our aim was to investigate the effect of RA treatment on differentiation and lipid accumulation in a Simpson-Golabi-Behmel syndrome (SGBS) cell strain, as a relevant human model system to study adipogenesis (Tews et al., 2019). Additionally, adipogenic and inflammatory factors were explored to further elucidate the underlying molecular mechanism of RA bioactivity in adipocytes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Cell culture medium Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium/Nutrient F-12 Ham (DMEM/F12), Oil Red O solution 0.5% in isopropanol (ORO), DMSO, isopropanol, 10% formalin, Bradford reagent, RIPA lysis buffer, protease and phosphatase inhibitor cocktail, fetal bovine serum (FBS), penicillin/streptomycin 10 000 IU/10 mg/mL (PS), biotin, pantothenic acid, human apo-transferrin, rosiglitazone, human insulin, 3-isobutyl-1-methylxanthine (IBXM), dexamethasone, triiodothyronine, cortisol, orlistat (ORST, $\geq 98\%$, Mw 495.73 g/mol) and rosmarinic acid ($\geq 98\%$, Mw 360.31 g/mol) were obtained from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). All chemical and reagents used to perform electrophoresis, immunoblotting and real-time quantitative reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) were purchased from Bio-Rad Laboratories Inc. (Hercules, CA, USA). Antibodies for western blotting were purchased as follows: rabbit anti-C/EBP α (#2295S) and anti-PPAR γ antibodies (#2443S) from Cell Signaling Technology (Leiden, The Netherlands); rabbit anti-adiponectin antibody (#GTX112777) from GeneTex Inc. (Irvine, CA, USA); hFAB rhodamine anti-tubulin

(#12004166), hFAB rhodamine anti-GAPDH (#12004168) and goat anti-rabbit IgG StarBright Blue 700 (#12004162) antibodies from Bio-Rad.

2.2. Cell culture and treatments

SGBS preadipocytes were cultured according to the established optimal conditions (Tews et al., 2019). Cells were grown in DMEM/F12 medium supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% PS solution, 33 μ M biotin and 17 μ M pantothenic acid at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere and air with fixed CO₂ content of 5%. Upon confluence adipogenic differentiation was induced with serum-free DMEM/F12 containing 1% PS, 33 μ M biotin, 17 μ M pantothenic acid, 2 μ M rosiglitazone, 10 μ g/mL apo-transferrin, 20 nM insulin, 25 nM dexamethasone, 500 μ M IBMX, 100 nM cortisol and 200 pM triiodothyronine. From the day 4 of differentiation and thereafter cells were maintained in serum-free DMEM/F12 with all aforementioned supplements, excluding IBMX, rosiglitazone and dexamethasone.

Treatment solutions were prepared from ORST and RA in DMSO and further diluted in the culture medium. To minimize the influence from the solvent the final concentration of the DMSO per well did not exceeded 0.02% and vehicle control group was included. Concentrations of 1, 5, and 25 μ M were selected for the RA and 5 μ M for the ORST, based on preliminary experiments. Treatment with ORST was included as positive control, as one of the most widely used anti-obesity drugs.

Cells were grouped as follows: non-differentiated SGBS preadipocytes (ND), differentiated SGBS adipocytes, vehicle treated (Vehicle), orlistat treated group as positive control (ORST), three experimental groups with the respective RA treatment concentrations (RA 1, RA 5 and RA 25). All treatments were added to the culture media when differentiation was initiated and were repeated with every next media replacement. Extraction of total RNA and proteins, lipid staining and adipolysis assessment were performed on the 9th day of differentiation 24 h after the last treatment. All assays included at least three technical replicates from three independent experiments (Fig. 1b).

2.3. Oil red O staining and quantification

Differentiated SGBS adipocytes were fixed with 10% formalin for 10 min at room temperature (RT), washed twice with ice-cold phosphate buffered saline and stained with the fresh filtered ORO dye solution for 15 min at RT. Photomicrographs of the stained cells were captured using an Oxion Inverso OX.2053-PLPH inverted microscope and DC.10000-Pro CMEX camera from Euromex (Arnhem, The Netherlands). The acquired images were analyzed with Image Focus Alpha software from Euromex.

The estimation of the total lipid content was done by extraction of the ORO dye from the cells with isopropanol for 10 min at RT followed by reading the absorbance at 495 nm on Anthos Zenyth 340 multiplate reader (Biochrome, Berlin, Germany).

2.4. Adipolysis assessment

Evaluation of basal lipolysis was measured in cell culture supernatant by Adipolysis assay kit (#MAK313) from Merck KGaA, following the manufacturer's protocol. Glycerol standard dilutions 10 μ L or supernatant sample were added to 100 μ L working reagent in 96-well plate. Following incubation of 20 min at RT the optical density was measured at 570 nm. Glycerol concentration (μ M) was calculated according to the obtained standard curve.

2.5. RT-qPCR

Total RNA was isolated using Quick-RNA Miniprep kit (#R1055) from Zymo Research (Irvine, CA, USA). Concentration and quality of the obtained total RNA samples were determined with Genova Nano micro-

volume spectrophotometer from Cole-Parmer (Staffordshire, UK) and by resolving on horizontal electrophoresis in 1% agarose gel. Synthesis of copy DNA from the extracted RNA samples was done with RevertAid First Strand cDNA synthesis kit (#1622) from ThermoFisher Scientific Inc. (Waltham, MA, USA). Real-time quantitative PCR (RT-qPCR) was performed on C1000 Touch thermal cycler and CFX96 detection system (Bio-Rad) using SsoFast EvaGreen Supermix (#1725204). Gene expression was quantified by the comparative threshold cycle ($\Delta\Delta CT$) method on the CFX Maestro software (Bio-Rad). Normalization was done to the expression of *RPL13A* and *TUBB* as reference genes. Primer sequences used for RT-qPCR were custom designed using Primer-BLAST (National Center for Biotechnology Information, U.S. National Library of Medicine, USA) and were listed in Table 1.

2.6. Western blot

Total protein lysates were prepared using RIPA buffer freshly supplemented with 1% protease and phosphatase inhibitor cocktail for 45 min on ice, followed by centrifugation (15000 rpm, 15 min, and 4 °C) and collection of the clear supernatant. The total protein concentration was determined using Bradford assay.

Equal amounts of total protein of 30 µg per lane were separated with vertical electrophoresis on 10% TGX Stain-Free SDS-PAGE gels and transferred to a polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membranes via semi-dry transfer with Trans-Blot Turbo transfer system (Bio-Rad). Following blocking for 1h at RT in Tris buffered saline with 1% (w/v) casein, the membranes were incubated with the primary rabbit antibodies against C/EBP α , PPAR γ or adiponectin overnight at 4 °C. For fluorescent detection of the target proteins StarBright Blue 700 goat anti-rabbit IgG secondary antibody was used. Tubulin or GAPDH were detected with direct primary antibodies and used as housekeeping proteins for normalization. The immunodetection was visualized with ChemiDoc MP imaging system (Bio-Rad) and the acquired images were analyzed with Image Lab software (Bio-Rad).

2.7. Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed with SigmaPlot software and presented as mean \pm SEM. Statistical significance between groups was determined by ANOVA, followed by Tukey's post hoc test. The distribution difference was determined by Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Values of $P < 0.05$ were considered to be significant.

Table 1
Primer sequences for the RT-qPCR.

Target gene (human)	Forward primer (5' - 3')	Length	Reverse primer (5' - 3')	Length	Tm f/r (°C)	Product length (bp)
<i>ACC</i>	TTCACCTCCACCTGTGTCAGCG	20	GTCAGAGAAGCAGCCCATCA	20	60.25/59.75	99
<i>ADIPOQ</i>	TGCCCAAAGAGGAGAGAGGAA	21	TCAGAAACAGGCACACAACCTCA	22	60.49/60.36	97
<i>CEBPA</i>	TATAGGCTGGGCTTCCCCTT	20	CTAGGTCTCCCTCTCCCACC	20	60.03/60.11	148
<i>FABP4</i>	ACCTTAGATGGGGGTGTCCT	20	TGCCAACTTCAGTCCAGGTC	20	59.58/59.97	177
<i>FASN</i>	TCTACGGCTCCACGCTCTT	19	GAAGAGTCTTCGTGAGCCAGG	21	60.68/60.40	130
<i>IL1B</i>	TGAGCTCGCCAGTGAATGA	20	AGATTCTGAGCTGGATGCCG	20	59.68/59.97	143
<i>IL10</i>	CGGCGCTGTATCGATTCT	20	AGTCGCCACCTGATGTCTC	20	61.15/61.61	186
<i>IL17A</i>	CTGTCCCATCCAGCAAGAG	20	AGGCCACATGTTGGACAATC	20	60.11/60.32	132
<i>NFE2L2</i>	TCTGACTCCGGCATTCTCACT	20	GGCACTGTCTAGCTCTTCCA	20	59.02/59.10	129
<i>NFKB1</i>	GAGCAAGATCAGGAGCCAG	20	TGTCAACCGGTAGTCGAAAA	20	60.18/59.97	171
<i>PGC1A</i>	AAATATCTGACCACAAAGCATGACC	25	GTTGGTTTGGCTTGTAAAGTGTGT	24	59.65/60.62	134
<i>PPARA</i>	CGGGATGCTGTGATGCGTATG	20	GCCAGGACGATCTCCACAG	19	60.67/59.86	187
<i>PPARD</i>	GGCTTCCACTACGGTGTTCAT	21	GGCACTTGTGTGGGTTCTT	19	60.34/59.27	130
<i>PPARG</i>	GATCCAGTGGTTGCAGATTACAA	23	GAGGAGTGGAAAGGCTCTTC	21	58.99/60.07	144
<i>RPL13A</i>	AAAAGCGGATGGTGGTTCCT	20	GCTGTCACTGCCTGGTACTT	20	59.89/59.96	118
<i>SREBP1</i>	TGTACTTCTGGAGGCATCGC	20	CTACAAGCCAGGTCCAGGTG	20	59.82/60.04	139
<i>TGFB1</i>	TACCTGAACCCGTGTGCTC	20	GTTGCTGAGGTATCGCCAGG	20	59.97/60.81	122
<i>TUBB</i>	AGCCGTCTTACTCAACTGCC	20	GTCACCCAGAATGGCAGAA	19	60.04/59.96	198
<i>UCP1</i>	GAAACAGCACCTAGTTTAGGAAGC	24	AGCCTTCGGTGTGTGCTATTATTCT	25	59.85/60.86	187

Abbreviations: bp, base pairs; Tm, melting temperature.

3. Results

3.1. Effect of rosmarinic acid on cell viability

Obesity is accompanied with adipose tissue inflammation (Boutens et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2020; Vasileva et al., 2020). Therefore, we predicted that RA could modulate the inflammatory response, as well as, adipogenesis in human adipocytes. In our preliminary experiments, concentrations of RA up to 100 µM did not affect cell viability in both SGBS preadipocytes and in differentiated SGBS adipocytes (Supp. fig. S1).

3.2. Rosmarinic acid suppresses adipogenesis and stimulates lipolysis in human adipocytes

To evaluate the potential influence by RA on adipogenesis and adipolysis we employed Oil Red O and glycerol release assays. ORST is a lipase inhibitor approved for long-term management in obesity (Vasileva et al., 2018). Inhibition of pancreatic lipase by ORST obstructs adipocyte hypertrophy without direct modulation of adipogenic factors in adipocytes (Gomma et al., 2019; Pai et al., 2019). Although ORO staining showed that ORST did not significantly affect adipogenesis (Fig. 2a and b), its wide use in obesity management defines it as a relevant reference compound for anti-obesity effect. Dose-dependent repression of adipogenesis was observed in the presence of RA on the microscopic images from the ORO staining on day 9 (Fig. 2a), as well as from the measurements of the extracted ORO dye absorbance exceeding the effect of ORST (Fig. 2b). Correspondingly, basal lipolysis was stimulated upon RA treatment in a dose-dependent manner that was assessed as an increase in glycerol release with over 30% compared to both to vehicle and positive control groups (Fig. 2c). These data suggested that RA is interfering with the processes of lipid accumulation and metabolism in adipocytes.

3.3. Rosmarinic acid downregulates adipogenic gene expression

To explore the molecular mechanisms of action of RA in adipocytes, key genes involved in different phases of the adipogenic pathway and fatty acids metabolism were evaluated by RT-qPCR. A distinct expression profile was observed for the non-differentiated SGBS pre-adipocytes (ND) compared to the vehicle treated SGBS adipocytes used as controls, which authenticated the successful differentiation process (Fig. 3). Downregulation was observed of the genes from the lipid metabolic pathway *ACC* (Fig. 3a), *FASN* (Fig. 3d), as well as, of *PPARD* (Fig. 3h)

Fig. 2. Rosmarinic acid promoted inhibition of lipid accumulation and induced basal lipolysis in human SGBS adipocytes. Representative microscopic images with 10x and 20x magnifications (scale bar 50 μm) from the Oil red O staining (a). Spectrophotometric measures of the absorbance of the extracted Oil red O dye at 495 nm (b). Glycerol concentration (μM) determined in cell culture media from day 9 of differentiation (c). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM, each experimental group consisted of at least six samples and three independent biological repeats. * $P < 0.05$ compared to vehicle control group. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

and *UCP1* (Fig. 3j) by the ORST treatment. In the presence of RA dose-dependent inhibition was found in the relative mRNA expression of both *ACC* (Fig. 3a) and *FASN* (Fig. 3d), as well as, of the *FABP4* (Fig. 3e) compared to the both vehicle and ORST treated adipocytes. In contrast, the changes observed for the adipogenic genes adiponectin (*ADIPOQ*, Fig. 3b) and *CEBPA* (Fig. 3c) were independent from the RA treatment concentration. The *ADIPOQ* expression was suppressed by RA 5 and only mildly influenced by the other two doses. Interestingly, the *CEBPA* gene expression was significantly downregulated upon RA treatment in the highest concentration of 25 μM while treatment with RA at 1 and 5 μM induced the opposite effect. The expression of the gene responsible for *de novo* lipogenesis and glucose utilization *SREBP1* (Fig. 3f) was

upregulated by the ORST treatment while RA dramatically suppressed its expression. In contrast to previous studies in other cell types (Yang et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2018; Zych et al., 2019), a decrease was detected in the expression of *PPARA* (Fig. 3g) and *PPARD* (Fig. 3h) but not *PPARG* (Fig. 3i) by the RA treatment.

Since pan-adipogenic markers were markedly decreased by RA, we further explored whether transdifferentiation towards brown/beige phenotype might be induced upon RA treatment. To test this hypothesis, the mRNA expression levels of major downstream browning genes uncoupling protein 1 (*UCP1*) and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma co-activator 1 alpha (*PGC1A*) were analyzed. A significant decrease in response to RA for both *UCP1* (Fig. 3j) and *PGC1A*

Fig. 3. Rosmarinic acid treatment resulted in decreased adipogenic gene expression. Relative mRNA expression normalized to vehicle control group for the following adipogenic genes: *ACC* (a), *ADIPOQ* (b), *CEBPA* (c), *FASN* (d), *FABP4* (e), *SREBP1* (f), *PPARA* (g), *PPARG* (h), *PPARG* (i), *UCP1* (j) and *PGC1A* (k) from the RT-qPCR. *RPL13A* and *TUBB* were used as reference genes. Each sample was tested in triplicates from three independent experiments. Data are presented in mean \pm SEM. * $P < 0.05$ compared to vehicle control group.

(Fig. 3k) was observed, results exclude browning induction by RA in human adipocytes. Taken together, the RT-qPCR analysis elucidated that RA attenuates adipogenesis through downregulation of multiple adipogenic and lipogenic genes in human adipocytes.

3.4. Rosmarinic acid targets C/EBP α and adiponectin in human adipocytes

Adipogenic differentiation is orchestrated in tandem by C/EBP α and PPAR γ , which activation results in formation of positive feedback loop and a subsequent increase in the level of related adipogenic markers such as FABP4, leptin and adiponectin (Lin et al., 2020; Vasileva et al., 2018). Since changes in the mRNA expression levels of *ADIPOQ* (Fig. 3b) and *CEBPA* (Fig. 3c) genes were observed upon RA treatment, we further directed our attention to the possible correspondence with alterations in respective protein translation. Therefore, we performed western blotting

to evaluate the effect of RA on the protein levels. Successful adipogenic differentiation was confirmed by the absence of C/EBP α (Fig. 4a), PPAR γ (Fig. 4b) and adiponectin (Fig. 4c) at protein level in the non-differentiated SGBS preadipocytes (ND) compared to vehicle treated controls. Elevation in C/EBP α and mild decrease in adiponectin levels were found in the ORST treated adipocytes. Although, RT-qPCR showed that RA did not significantly affect *PPARG* (Fig. 3i) mRNA expression, however, PPAR γ was inhibited upon RA treatment at the protein level (Fig. 4b). Western blotting also showed C/EBP α (Fig. 4a) and adiponectin (Fig. 4c) were dose-dependently downregulated by the RA treatment compared to both vehicle and ORST treated controls. Thus, these key adipogenic proteins may serve as potential direct targets for RA in adipocytes.

Fig. 4. Rosmarinic acid reduced C/EBP α , PPAR γ and adiponectin protein production in human SGBS adipocytes. Western blot performed to examine the protein level of C/EBP α (a), PPAR γ (b) and adiponectin (c). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM and are representative of three independent experiments. *P < 0.05 compared to vehicle control group.

3.5. Rosmarinic acid modulates inflammatory and oxidative stress factors in adipocytes

We employed RT-qPCR to further investigate whether the anti-adipogenic effects of RA eventually correlates with modulation of genes involved in the inflammatory response in human SGBS adipocytes. As expected, upon RA treatment we observed a dose-dependent decrease in the mRNA expression of *IL1B* (Fig. 5a) and *TGF1B* (Fig. 5b) exceeding the effect of the positive control. Conversely, elevation was found in the

mRNA expression levels of *IL17A* (Fig. 5c) and the anti-inflammatory marker *IL10* (Fig. 5d) by the RA treatment. In addition, the RT-qPCR results indicated that in human adipocytes the *NFE2L2* (Fig. 5e) mRNA expression levels were moderately downregulated by both ORST and RA. However, the expression of the *NFKB1* (Fig. 5f) was slightly upregulated by the RA treatment. Additionally, the mRNA expression levels of *TNFA* and *IL6* were not significantly affected upon RA treatment (Supp. fig. S2). These data suggest that RA prevents obesity-related inflammation by modulating the autocrine inflammatory response in

Fig. 5. Rosmarinic acid modulated inflammation in human adipocytes. Relative expression of mRNA normalized to vehicle control group for the genes of the following cytokines: *IL1B* (a), *TGF1B* (b), *IL17A* (c), *IL10* (d), *NFE2L2* (e), *NFKB1* (f) from the RT-qPCR. Normalization was done to *RPL13A* and *TUBB* as reference genes. For this gene study, data are presented in mean \pm SEM and are representative from three independent experimental differentiations. *P < 0.05 compared to vehicle control group.

human adipocytes.

3.6. Proposed mechanism for the anti-adipogenic activity of rosmarinic acid

We next combined the obtained data to develop a model of the potential mechanism of action of rosmarinic acid. Taken together, our findings suggest that the molecular interaction of RA with adipogenic genes along with suppression of the downstream translation of C/EBP α , PPAR γ and adiponectin are directly involved in the observed anti-adipogenic activity (Fig. 6). Potential involvement of the RA in the induction of browning in human adipocytes was not confirmed. Modulation of cytokines and key transcription factors from the inflammatory pathways is eventually connected with the RA anti-adipogenic effect.

4. Discussion

Commitment to adipogenic differentiation in preadipocytes is induced upon hormonal stimulation by increase in certain growth factors and cytokines such as IGF1, IL-6, TGF- β , TNF- α and IL-17A (Boutens et al., 2018; Cen et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2020; Shin et al., 2009; Stechschultze et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2012). *De novo* adipogenesis is proposed as beneficial in obese states lacking metabolic complications (Senol-Cosar et al., 2016; Shao et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020). However, within the context of obesity-induced adipose tissue inflammation as a modality of obesity adipogenesis suppression is favorable approach to restrict metabolic complications (Lin et al., 2020; Vasileva et al., 2020; Wueest et al., 2018). Accordingly, employing compounds that simultaneously target adipogenesis and attenuate obesity-related inflammation emerged as an attractive strategy for obesity management.

Induction of white adipogenic differentiation transforms the fibroblast-like preadipocytes into round-shape adipocytes accumulating intracellular lipid droplets. Mature adipocytes maintain their energy storage function by balancing between the processes of free fatty acids accumulation and release, namely adipogenesis and adipolysis (Arner et al., 2019; Boutens et al., 2018; Qiao et al., 2011). In the present study, RA treatment in human adipocytes suppressed lipid accumulation, enhanced lipolysis and downregulated key adipogenic factors to an extent exceeding that of ORST.

The members of the C/EBP family of transcription factors participate as critical regulators throughout the development of adipogenic differentiation. Whereas in the early stages C/EBP- β and - δ are predominantly involved, later stages of adipocytes maturation are governed by the C/EBP α protein (Lin et al., 2020; Shao et al., 2018; Vasileva et al., 2018). In this regard, our findings that RA significantly and dose-dependently

downregulated C/EBP α at a protein level suggested that RA may exert its bioactivity mainly through inhibition of this key adipogenic transcription factor through a post-translational modification. The discrepancy found between the effect of RA at the lower concentrations of 1 and 5 μ M on the mRNA expression and protein levels of C/EBP α could be a reflection of a compensatory upregulation in the *CEPBA* transcription following RA-induced suppression at an earlier time-point. The marked decrease of *SREBP1* expression support this statement, as this factor is in close coordination with *CEPBA* during adipogenic differentiation. Furthermore, inhibition of the SREBP1-mediated pathway is associated with decreased production of TNF- α , IL-6, adiponectin and resistin in adipocytes (Okuno et al., 2018). In accordance to that, the downregulation of CEBP α and SREBP1 in our study could be related to the inhibitory effect on adiponectin and FABP4 by the RA treatment in adipocytes. In addition, the activation of ACC and FASN, which act as key enzymes in the lipid synthesis pathway in adipocytes, is directly dependent on SREBP1 (Boutens et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2020; Okuno et al., 2018). In our study, we found that RA downregulated both ACC and FASN expression in adipocytes. Therefore, our findings suggested that RA interfered with the process of lipid metabolism.

The PPARs nuclear receptor superfamily is represented by PPAR- α , - γ and - β/δ with each member exerting tissue-specific regulatory functions (Cen et al., 2020; Chehaibi et al., 2015; Massaro et al., 2016; Stechschultze et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2012). PPAR α and PPAR β/δ are predominantly expressed in hepatocytes and muscle cells, respectively, while PPAR γ is most abundant in adipocytes (Chehaibi et al., 2015; Massaro et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2012). In tandem with C/EBP α , PPAR γ is considered as a master regulator of adipogenic differentiation in adipose tissue (Boutens et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2020; Stechschultze et al., 2016). Furthermore, except its role in regulating insulin sensitivity in adipose tissue, PPAR γ is involved in maintaining the balance between osteoclast and osteoblast differentiation (Massaro et al., 2016; Stechschultze et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2012). These key functions and its abundance in different tissues make PPAR γ one of the most attractive targets in the management of obesity, type 2 diabetes, hepatic steatosis and osteoporosis prevention (Barroso et al., 2015; Chehaibi et al., 2015; Li et al., 2020). Interestingly, PPAR γ was negatively affected by the RA treatment in our study, which finding is inconsistent with previous studies regarding the action of RA on PPAR γ (Yang et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2018; Zych et al., 2018). The antifibrotic effect of RA on cardiac fibroblast, through stimulation of AMPK and inhibition of TGF- β /SMAD3 pathways activation, is reported to be PPAR γ -dependent (Zhang et al., 2018). However, an evaluation of RA antifibrotic action in a cadmium-induced renal fibrosis model reported AMPK/TGF- β /SMAD3 as the main pathway influenced without PPAR γ participation (Joardar

Fig. 6. Proposed mechanism of the anti-adipogenic effect of the rosmarinic acid.

et al., 2019). Another study investigating the antifibrotic effect of RA in hepatocytes also found an increase in PPAR γ levels (Yang et al., 2012). One possible explanation for the discrepancy between these studies and our results could be cell type specific action of RA on PPAR γ . Moreover, apart from *PPARG*, downregulation was found for both *PPARA* and *PPARD* mRNA expression in our study. Given the similarity between the three subclasses of PPARs and their overlapping involvement in the metabolic pathways across various tissues (Barroso et al., 2015; Chehaibi et al., 2015; Li et al., 2020; Zych et al., 2019) a potential activity of RA on PPAR α and PPAR β/δ in adipocytes warrants further investigation.

Adiponectin is one of the most exhaustively studied adipokines and both its physiological and pathological effects are well described (Qiao et al., 2011; Straub et al., 2019; Straub and Scherer, 2019; Vasileva et al., 2018; Wentworth et al., 2017). Although adiponectin levels are found to be low in obese individuals (Qiao et al., 2011; Straub and Scherer, 2019) its levels increase during adipogenic differentiation, which corresponds to promoting proper insulin sensitivity in the mature adipocyte (Straub et al., 2019; Wentworth et al., 2017). In our study, we found that RA decreased adiponectin protein expression in adipocytes which was only partly corresponding from the effect of RA on the respective gene expression levels. The lack of match in the effect of RA on adiponectin gene and protein expression levels worth further detailed investigations, however, it could be explained with the substantial role of regulatory processes occurring at post-transcriptional, translational levels, as well as, at protein degradation regulation (Stechschulte et al., 2016; Vogel and Marcotte, 2012). Furthermore, we could speculate that the observed reduction in adiponectin levels is a consequence from the inhibitory effect demonstrated by RA on the adipogenic master regulators C/EBP α and PPAR γ .

Previously reported activities of RA are mostly explained by its interference with cellular and molecular pathways of the inflammatory response and the response to oxidative burden such as NF κ B/MAPK (Chen et al., 2018; Joardar et al., 2019; Seow and Lau, 2017), AMPK/TGF- β /SMAD (Yang et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2018) and NRF2/HO-1 pathways (Gerogianni et al., 2018; Joardar et al., 2019). The activity of RA towards resolution of inflammation has been shown to target key transcription factors such as NRF2 and NF κ B in different tissues such as neurons (Gerogianni et al., 2018; Rong et al., 2018), nephrons (Joardar et al., 2019), keratinocytes (Georgiev et al., 2012), and chondrocytes (Chen et al., 2018). In the present study, NF κ B expression was upregulated upon RA treatment in adipocytes, which is in contrast to the overall inhibitory effect on pro-inflammatory cytokines. We speculate that the observed effect might be due to tissue specific action of RA on NF κ B signaling in adipocytes.

The transcription factor NRF2 regulates numerous genes from the cellular defense against oxidative stress and the metabolic biotransformation of xenobiotics such as HO-1, glutathione S-transferase, and NAD (P)H quinone oxidoreductase (Barroso et al., 2015; Li et al., 2020; Rong et al., 2018; Vasileva et al., 2020). Tissue-specific inhibition of NRF2 activity is favorable in liver as therapeutic strategy against hepatosteatosis progression (Li et al., 2020). Activation of NRF2 *in vitro* and *in vivo* in high fructose-fed mice resulted in development of insulin resistance and chronic inflammation in adipocytes (Barroso et al., 2015). Correspondingly, our results indicate that RA represses NRF2 in SGBS adipocytes which could be, at least partly, related to its anti-adipogenic effect. Interference of the NRF2-mediated response in adipocytes is incompletely understood, especially during differentiation (Vasileva et al., 2020), and the observed effect by the RA treatment merits further investigation.

Recent findings on the function of TGF- β in adipose tissue function reveal its crucial role during the induction phase of the physiological process of differentiation (Lin et al., 2020; Petrus et al., 2018; Wuest et al., 2018). However, TGF- β , IL-6 and IL-1 β overexpression in obese fat tissue could lead to aggravation of obesity-induced inflammation and decreased insulin sensitivity (Kroon et al., 2020; Okuno et al., 2018; Shin et al., 2009). Hence, neutralization of the pro-inflammatory cytokines

production in adipocytes is a strategy in the obesity management (Lin et al., 2020; Vasileva et al., 2018). Previous studies have reported that RA-induced downregulation of *TGF1B* and *IL1B* *in vitro* models is related to its antifibrotic and anti-inflammatory effects (Georgiev et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2018). Correspondingly, we found that RA downregulated TGF- β and IL-1 β , which implied that RA might not only reduce obesity-related inflammation, but also indirectly improve insulin sensitivity.

Regulatory role in human adipocytes is suggested for the cytokine IL-17A, which is multidirectional and depending from presence or absence of concomitant obesity pathology (Shin et al., 2009; Yu et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2012). In the context of obesity and accompanying ovarian and prostate cancer mechanistic link was proposed between FABP4 signaling and IL-17A, resulting in accelerated cell growth (Yu et al., 2020). Conversely, treatment with IL-17A itself in human differentiating adipocytes increased lipolysis rates and decreased adipocyte size (Shin et al., 2009). In our study, RA increased *IL17A* expression levels in human adipocytes. It is possible that the observed modulation in *IL17A* levels correlates with the marked suppression in the lipogenic genes *ACC*, *FASN* and *FABP4*. The influence of RA on *IL17A* has not been reported previously in adipocytes, so identifying whether and how this compound affects the cytokine pathway in the context of obesity is needed.

The increase in IL-10 *in vivo* is found to be of a key role in the defense of white adipose tissue against inflammation (Wu et al., 2019). Interestingly, IL-10 treatment in adipocytes revealed marked suppression of the browning differentiation program by selectively antagonizing *CEBPB*, *PGC1A* and *UCP1* gene expression (Rajbhandari et al., 2018). In the current study, our results showed that RA promoted an increase in *IL10* gene expression in adipocytes. This further validates that the anti-inflammatory effect of this compound contributes to the mechanism of its anti-adipogenic action. We hypothesized that the downregulation of *PGC1A* and *UCP1* expression observed on RA treatment could be a result from the elevated levels of *IL10* and intrinsic regulatory cytokines activity within adipocytes. Although many recent studies have targeted induction of browning in white adipocytes as a promising approach in obesity management (Rajbhandari et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2015), we did not observe such potential by RA treatment.

In summary, our findings demonstrate that RA promotes anti-adipogenic and anti-inflammatory activity in human SGBS cells. We have identified C/EBP α as the most probable direct target for the molecular regulation of adipogenic differentiation by RA. In addition, we have provided evidence that modulation of the TGF- β /IL-17A signaling play a role in inflammatory processes in human adipocytes and could be at least partly related to the RA anti-adipogenic activity. We conclude that RA merits future examinations within *in vivo* settings and is a potential candidate for treatment of obesity and obesity-related inflammation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lily V. Vasileva: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Martina S. Savova: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Daniel Tews: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Martin Wabitsch: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Milen I. Georgiev: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This research received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, project PlantaSYST (SGA No 739582 under FPA No. 664620), and the BG05M2OP001-1.003-001-C01 project, financed by the European Regional Development Fund through the "Science and Education for Smart Growth" Operational Programme.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2021.112002>.

References

- Arner, P., Bernard, S., Appelsved, L., Fu, K.Y., Andersson, D.P., Salehpour, M., Thorell, A., Ryden, M., Spalding, K.L., 2019. Adipose lipid turnover and long-term changes in body weight. *Nat. Med.* 25, 1385–1389.
- Barroso, E., Rodriguez-Rodriguez, R., Chacon, M.R., Maymo-Masip, E., Ferrer, L., Salvado, L., Salmeron, E., Wabitsch, M., Palomer, X., Vendrell, J., Wahli, W., Vazquez-Carrera, M., 2015. PPAR β/δ ameliorates fructose-induced insulin resistance in adipocytes by preventing Nrf2 activation. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 1852, 1049–1058.
- Blüher, M., 2019. Obesity: global epidemiology and pathogenesis. *Nat. Rev. Endocrinol.* 15, 288–298.
- Boutens, L., Hooiveld, G., Dhingra, S., Cramer, R.A., Netea, M.G., Stienstra, R., 2018. Unique metabolic activation of adipose tissue macrophages in obesity promotes inflammatory responses. *Diabetologia* 61, 942–953.
- Cen, S., Li, J., Cai, Z., Pan, Y., Sun, Z., Li, Z., Ye, G., Zheng, G., Li, M., Liu, W., Wang, S., Xie, Z., Wang, P., Shen, H., 2020. TRAF4 acts as a fate checkpoint to regulate the adipogenic differentiation of MSCs by activating PKM2. *EBioMedicine* 54, 102722.
- Chehaibi, K., Cedó, L., Metso, J., Palomer, X., Santos, D., Quesada, H., Slimane, M.N., Wahli, W., Julve, J., Vazquez-Carrera, M., Jauhainen, M., Blanco-Vaca, F., Escalá-Gil, J.C., 2015. PPAR- β/δ activation promotes phospholipid transfer protein expression. *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 94, 101–108.
- Chen, W.P., Jin, G., Xiong, Y., Hu, P.F., Bao, J.P., Wu, L.D., 2018. Rosmarinic acid down-regulates NO and PGE₂ expression via MAPK pathway in rat chondrocytes. *J. Cell Mol. Med.* 22, 346–353.
- Filipe, H.A.L., Sousa, C., Marques, J.T., Vila-Vicosa, D., de Granada-Flor, A., Viana, A.S., Santos, M.S.C.S., Machuqueiro, M., de Almeida, R.F.M., 2018. Differential targeting of membrane lipid domains by caffeic acid and its ester derivatives. *Free Radic. Biol. Med.* 115, 232–245.
- Georgiev, M.I., Pastore, S., Lulli, D., Alipieva, K., Kostyuk, V., Potapovich, A., Panetta, M., Korikina, L., 2012. Verbascum xanthopheniceum-derived phenylethanoid glycosides are potent inhibitors of inflammatory chemokines in dormant and interferon-gamma-stimulates human keratinocytes. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 144, 754–760.
- Gerogianni, P.S., Chatzithanasiadou, M.V., Diamantis, D.A., Tzakos, A.G., Galaris, D., 2018. Lipophilic ester and amide derivatives of rosmarinic acid protect cells against H2O2-induced DNA damage and apoptosis: the potential role of intracellular accumulation and labile iron chelation. *Redox Biol.* 15, 548–556.
- Gomma, A., Farhaly, H., El-Sers, D., Farrag, M., Al-Zokeim, N., 2019. Inhibition of adiposity and related metabolic disturbances by polyphenol-rich extract of *Boswellia serrata* gum through alternation of adipo/cytokine profiles. *Inflammopharmacology* 27, 549–559.
- Joardar, S., Dewanjee, S., Bjowmick, S., Dua, T.K., Das, S., Saha, A., Feo, V.D., 2019. Rosmarinic acid attenuates cadmium-induced nephrotoxicity via inhibition of oxidative stress, apoptosis, inflammation and fibrosis. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 20, 2027.
- Kim, O.Y., Chung, J.Y., Song, J., 2019. Effect of resveratrol on adipokines and myokines involved in fat browning: Perspectives in healthy weight against obesity. *Pharmacol. Res.* 148, 104411.
- Kroon, T., Harms, M., Maurer, S., Bonnet, L., Alexandersson, I., Lindblom, A., Ahnmark, A., Nilsson, D., Gennemark, P., O'Mahony, G., Osinski, V., McNamara, C., Boucher, J., 2020. PPAR γ and PPAR α synergize to induce robust browning of white fat in vivo. *Mol. Metab.* 36, 100964.
- Li, L., Fu, J., Liu, D., Sun, J., Hou, Y., Chen, C., Shao, J., Wang, L., Wang, X., Zhao, R., Wang, H., Andersen, M.E., Zhang, Q., Xu, Y., Pi, J., 2020. Hepatocyte-specific Nrf2 deficiency mitigates high-fat diet-induced hepatic steatosis: involvement of reduced PPAR γ expression. *Redox Biol.* 30, 101412.
- Lin, T.Y., Chiu, C.J., Kuan, C.H., Chen, F.H., Shen, Y.C., Wu, C.H., Hsu, Y.H., 2020. IL-29 promoted obesity-induced inflammation and insulin resistance. *Cell. Mol. Immunol.* 17, 369–379.
- Massaro, M., Scoditti, E., Pellegrino, M., Carluccio, M.A., Calabriso, N., Wabitsch, M., Storelli, C., Wright, M., De Caterina, R., 2016. Therapeutic potential of the dual peroxisome proliferator activated receptor (PPAR) α/γ agonist aleglitazar in attenuating TNF- α -mediated inflammation and insulin resistance in human. *Pharmacol. Res.* 107, 125–136.
- Min, J., Chen, H., Gong, Z., Lin, X., Wu, T., Li, W., Fang, J., Huang, T., Zhang, Y., Zhao, W., Zhu, C., Wang, Q., Mi, S., Wang, N., 2018. Pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties of rosmarinic acid in rat cholestatic liver injury. *Molecules* 23, 2287.
- Okuno, Y., Fukuhara, A., Hashimoto, E., Kobayashi, H., Kobayashi, S., Otsuki, M., Shimomura, I., 2018. Oxidative stress inhibits healthy adipose tissue expansion through suppression of SREBP1-mediated lipogenic pathway. *Diabetes* 67, 1113–1127.
- Pai, S.A., Munshi, R., Panchal, F., Gaur, I., Mestry, S., Gursahani, M., Juvekar, A.R., 2019. Plumbagin reduces obesity and nonalcoholic fatty liver disease induced by fructose in rats through regulation of lipid metabolism, inflammation and oxidative stress. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* 111, 686–694.
- Petrus, P., Mejhert, N., Corrales, P., Lecourte, S., Li, Q., Maldonado, E., Kulyte, A., Lopez, Y., Campbell, M., Acosta, J.R., Laurencikienė, J., Douagi, I., Gao, H., Martínez-Alvarez, C., Heden, P., Spalding, K.L., Vidal-Puig, A., Medina-Gomez, G., Arner, P., Ryden, M., 2018. Transforming growth factor - β 3 regulates adipocyte number in subcutaneous white adipose tissue. *Cell Rep.* 25, 551–560.
- Qiao, L., Kinney, B., Schaak, J., Shao, J., 2011. Adiponectin inhibits lipolysis in mouse adipocytes. *Diabetes* 60, 1519–1521.
- Rajbhandari, P., Thomas, B.J., Feng, A.C., Hong, C., Wang, J., Vergnes, L., Sallam, T., Wang, B., Sandhu, J., Seldin, M.M., Lusis, A.J., Fong, J.G., Katz, M., Lee, R., Young, S.G., Reue, K., Smale, S.T., Tontonoz, P., 2018. IL-10 signaling remodels adipose tissue chromatin architecture to limit thermogenesis and energy expenditure. *Cell* 172, 218–233.
- Rong, H., Liang, Y., Niu, Y., 2018. Rosmarinic acid attenuates β -amyloid-induced oxidative stress via Akt/GSK3 β /Fyn-mediated Nrf2 activation in PC12 cells. *Free Radic. Biol. Med.* 120, 114–123.
- Shao, M., Vishvanath, L., Busbuco, N.C., Hepler, C., Shan, B., Sharma, A.X., Chen, S., Yu, X., An, Y.A., Zhu, Y., Holland, W.L., Gupta, R.K., 2018. De novo adipocyte differentiation from Pdgfr β ⁺ preadipocytes protects against pathologic visceral adipocyte tissue expansion in obesity. *Nat. Commun.* 9, 890.
- Senol-Cosar, O., Flash, R.J.R., DiStefano, M., Chawla, A., Nicoloso, S., Straubhaar, J., Hardy, O.T., Noh, H.L., Kim, J.K., Wabitsch, M., Scherer, P.E., Czech, M.P., 2016. Tenomodulin promotes human adipocyte differentiation and beneficial visceral adipose tissue expansion. *Nat. Commun.* 7, 10686.
- Seow, C.L., Lau, A.J., 2017. Differential activation of pregnane X receptor by carnosic acid, carnosol, ursolic acid and rosmarinic acid. *Pharmacol. Res.* 120, 23–33.
- Shin, J.H., Shin, D.W., Noh, M., 2009. Interleukin-17A inhibits adipocyte differentiation in human mesenchymal stem cells and regulates pro-inflammatory responses in adipocytes. *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 77, 1835–1844.
- Stechschulte, L.A., Czernik, P.J., Rotter, Z.C., Tausif, F.N., Corzo, C.A., Marciano, D.P., Asteian, A., Zheng, J., Kamenecka, T.M., Rosen, C.J., Griffin, P.R., Lecka-Czernik, B., 2016. PPAR γ post-translational modifications regulate bone formation and bone resorption. *EBioMedicine* 10, 174–184.
- Straub, L.G., Efthymiou, V., Grandl, G., Balaz, M., Challa, T.D., Truscello, L., Horvath, C., Moser, C., Rachmin, Y., Arnold, M., Sun, W., Modica, S., Wolfrum, C., 2019. Antioxidants protect against diabetes by improving glucose homeostasis in mouse models of inducible insulin resistance and obesity. *Diabetologia* 62, 2094–2105.
- Straub, L.G., Scherer, P.E., 2019. Metabolic messengers: adiponectin. *Nat. Metab.* 1, 334–339.
- Tews, D., Pula, T., Funcke, J.B., Jastroch, M., Keuper, M., Debatin, K.M., Wabitsch, M., Fischer-Posovszky, P., 2019. Elevated UCP1 levels are sufficient to improve glucose uptake in human white adipocytes. *Redox Biol.* 26, 101286.
- Vasileva, L.V., Marche, A.S., Georgiev, M.I., 2018. Causes and solutions to "globesity": the new fa(s)t alarming global epidemic. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 121, 173–193.
- Vasileva, L.V., Savova, M.S., Amirova, K.M., Dinkova-Kostova, A.T., Georgiev, M.I., 2020. Obesity and NRF2-mediated cytoprotection: where is the missing link? *Pharmacol. Res.* 156, 104760.
- Vogel, C., Marcotte, E.M., 2012. Insights into the regulation of protein abundance from proteomic and transcriptomic analyses. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 13, 227–232.
- Wang, S., Liang, S., Yang, G., Fu, X., Rogers, C.J., Zhu, M., Rodgers, B.D., Jiang, Q., Dodson, M.V., Min, D., 2015. Resveratrol induces brown-like adipocyte formation in white fat through activation of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) α 1. *Int. J. Obes.* 39, 967–976.
- Wang, S.P., Cao, S., Arhatte, M., Li, D., Shi, Y., Kurz, S., Hu, J., Wang, L., Shao, J., Atzberger, A., Wang, Z., Wang, C., Zang, W., Fleming, I., Wettschreck, N., Honore, E., Offermanns, S., 2020. Adipocyte Piezo 1 mediates obesogenic adipogenesis through the FGF1/FGFR1 signaling pathway in mice. *Nat. Commun.* 11, 2303.
- Wentworth, J.M., Zhang, J., Bandala-Sanchez, E., Naseli, G., Liu, C., Ritchie, M., Smyth, G.K., O'Brien, P.E., Harrison, L.C., 2017. Interferon-gamma released from omental adipose tissue of insulin-resistant humans alters adipocyte phenotype and impairs response to insulin and adiponectin release. *Int. J. Obes.* 41, 1782–1789.
- Wu, L., Dalal, R., Cao, C.D., Postoaik, J.L., Yang, G., Zhang, Q., Wang, Z., Lal, H., Kaer, L.V., 2019. IL-10-producing B cells are enriched in murine pericardial adipose tissues and ameliorate the outcome of acute myocardial infarction. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 16, 21673–21684.
- Wueest, S., Laesser, C.I., Boni-Schnetzler, M., Item, F., Lucchini, F.C., Borsigova, M., Müller, W., Donath, M.Y., Konrad, D., 2018. IL-6-type cytokines signaling in adipocytes induces intestinal GLP-1 secretion. *Diabetes* 67, 36–45.
- Yang, M.D., Chiang, Y.M., Higashiyama, R., Asahina, K., Mann, D.A., Mann, J., Wang, C.C., Tsukamoto, H., 2012. Rosmarinic acid and baicalin epigenetically derepress peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ in hepatic stellate cells for their antifibrotic effect. *Hepatology* 55, 1271–1281.
- Yu, C., Niu, X., Du, Y., Chen, Y., Liu, X., Xu, L., Iwakura, Y., Ma, X., Li, Y., Li, Y., Yao, Z., Deng, W., 2020. IL-17A promotes fatty acid uptake through the IL-17A/IL-17RA/p-STAT3/FABP4 axis to fuel ovarian cancer growth in an adipocyte-rich microenvironment. *Cancer Immunol. Immunother.* 69, 115–126.

- Zhang, M.A., Rego, D., Moshkova, M., Kebir, H., Chruscinski, A., Nguyen, H.K., Akkermann, R., Stanczyk, F.Z., Prat, A., Steiman, L., Dunn, S.E., 2012. Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR) α and γ regulate INF γ and IL-17A production by human T cells in sex-specific way. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 109, 9505–9510.
- Zhang, X., Ma, Z., Yuan, Y., Xu, S.C., Wei, W.Y., Song, P., Kong, C.Y., Deng, W., Tang, Q. Z., 2018. Rosmarinic acid attenuates cardiac fibrosis following long-term pressure overload via AMPK α /Smad3 signaling. *Cell Death Dis.* 9, 102.
- Zych, M., Wojnar, W., Borymski, S., Szlabaska, K., Bramora, P., Kaczmarczyk-Sedlak, I., 2019. Effect of rosmarinic acid on oxidative stress parameters in the cardiac tissue and serum of type 2 diabetic female rats. *Antioxidants* 8, 579.